
UNDERSTANDING THE PIVOTAL DIFFERENCES BETWEEN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL FINANCE

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Abstract

Modern Islamic finance tries to offer practising Muslims financial solutions according to the teachings of Islam. People are often not convinced whether these solutions are really genuine solutions or only simple imitations of conventional financial products. This paper shows the essential difference in the approach of conventional and Islamic finance by analysing the rules with regard to the prohibition of riba (interest) and gharar (excessive risk) in Islam. The results show that interest will inevitably lead to micro- and macroeconomic problems due to its unjust nature. Furthermore, gharar is an element which can be found in modern insurance contracts, and also leads to an unjust outcome between contracting parties. These prohibitions have the goal that neither contracting party will be able to abuse its economic power in any way.

Keywords: Islamic economics, Islamic finance, interest rate, riba, gharar.

INTRODUCTION

Islamic economics is seen as a new scientific field, even younger than modern economics. However this statement is not true, because Islamic economics is based on the sources of Islam – the Qur’an and the Sunnah (the practice of Prophet Muhammad, p.b.u.h.) and therefore exists since the beginning of Islam. But, it is true that the science of economics has to adapt according to new circumstances. The rules from the Qur’an and the Sunnah have to be understood in its essence in order to be implemented in the modern world. Therefore, modern Islamic economics can develop into three directions: ignorance, imitation or innovation. There is a group of Muslims ignoring the “economic rules” mentioned in the sources of Islam and this minority is imitating mainstream economic thinking by reducing the commandments and prohibitions mentioned in the Shari’ah exclusively to acts of worship. On the other hand, some Islamic economists try to use classic contracts and fit them into a modern context, often by giving them beautiful Arabic names, but also ignoring some basic laws of human behaviour and economics. The result of this engineering is often that we have complex contracts, which are less efficient than conventional financial contracts. Therefore, it is necessary to innovate, not by ignoring the commandments and prohibitions in the Qur’an and Sunnah, but by providing new solutions considering the intentions of the sources of Islam. This need is especially important in the field of finance, because the prohibition of riba (interest) in Islam implies the development of a completely different financial system. In order to carry out such a

“financial engineering”, it is necessary to understand the pivotal differences between Islamic and conventional finance; in order to avoid the problems caused conventional finance.

In this paper, we will concentrate our analysis on three important topics:

1. Ethical norms of the Islamic economic system
2. Understanding the prohibition of *riba* (interest)
3. Understanding the prohibition of *gharar* (excessive risk)

ETHICAL NORMS OF THE ISLAMIC ECONOMIC SYSTEM

Every person acts according to some rules – even acting without concrete rules constitutes a rule. Therefore, in order to understand a Muslim economic agent, it is necessary to understand his/her beliefs (i.e. the ethical framework), which command his/her behaviour. Ethics in Arabic is “akhlaq” and the singular is “khuluq”, a term that is mentioned directly in the Qur’an. (Abdullah, et al., 2018) The field of akhlaq covers different norms defining the behaviour of a Muslim. The ethical framework is a segment which is ignored in conventional economics. Since Lionel Robbins (1898-1984) declared a separation between ethics and economics in the 1930s, the prefix “political” has been removed from economics and defined the latter as a science. (Abdullah, et al., 2018) Such an approach is contrary to Islamic belief. Therefore, we will present shortly some basic foundations of the ethical framework in Islam.

TAWHID (ONENESS OF ALLAH)

The Islamic economic system is based on religious rules. This system has not only a secular dimension, but also a spiritual one. The central aspect of Islamic thinking is “tawhid”. Tawhid means the Oneness of Allah (God), i.e. monotheism. This means that there is no other God than Allah and that He is the Creator of everything. Allah, s.w.t., describes Himself in Qur’an in the following way:

“Say (O Muhammad (Peace be upon him)): "He is Allah, (the) One. (1) "Allah-us-Samad (The Self-Sufficient Master, Whom all creatures need, He neither eats nor drinks). (2) "He begets not, nor was He begotten; (3) "And there is none co-equal or comparable unto Him."” (4).” (Qur’an, 112: 1-4)

This chapter in the Qur’an (Surah) gives answers to the questions: who is Allah? Who is the God of the Muslims? The answer is that there is only one God, i.e. Allah, s.w.t. He is unique, nobody is similar to Him, He has neither an aide nor a partner. He is perfect in all His attributes and doings. (Ibn Kesir, 2002) Furthermore, Allah is the cause of everything, i.e. everything – being material or immaterial – is created by Allah.

Knowledge of tawhid has concrete consequences for the way of life of every believer. Due to this knowledge, every believer knows that every event in this world has its ultimate cause - and that is Allah, the Exalted. Thus, every believer knows that what he earns does not have an exclusive cause in his effort and his abilities, but that these abilities and provisions have been given from Allah.

HUMANS ARE VICEGERENTS OF ALLAH

The knowledge of tawhid implies that humans have been created as a “vicegerent” on earth. This “stewardship” is based on a “contract” between a human being and his Creator. With this contract, the human being recognises that Allah, s.w.t., is the real owner of everything existing. Allah, s.w.t., says in the Qur’an: **“To Allah belongs whatever is in the heavens and whatever is in the earth.” (Qur’an, 2: 284)**

Accepting this fact, an individual recognises to respect the laws of Allah, because a person will be held accountable for every act done on this world. This is the reason why Islam also regulates worldly matters. The divine message is a divine guidance by Allah which is sent down to be followed by human beings. It provides fundamental guidelines of what is good and bad for people and shows the general consequences of alternative paths in order to help them choose the right line of action. (Abdullah, et al., 2018) However, these laws are not so detailed that they ignore human reasoning and intellect. But, on the other hand, they are not so few or imprecise so that people could determine these laws according their interests. Far from these two extremes, Islam has a balanced approach towards regulating human lives. (Usmani, 2003) Islam gives humans a large array, where they can decide rationally which solution is the best for them. However, some questions, where humans are unable to give a right judgement, the Lawgiver gave a precise rule.

TAQWA

The term “taqwa” describes the constant awareness of Allah in the form of piousness, fear of Allah and love for Allah. Taqwa is mentioned many times in the Qur’an, such as: **“O you who have believed, fear Allah and speak words of appropriate justice.” (Qur’an, 33:7)** The reason for this is that the human race is created by Allah in order to worship Him. Allah, s.w.t., says in the Qur’an: **“And I did not create the jinn and mankind except to worship Me.” (Qur’an, 51:56)**

Every action will have its reaction, i.e. after death there will be Resurrection and Judgement with reward and punishment for every action done. Even in this world there will be a reaction, but the final accountability will happen after death. Taqwa is the continuous motivation for worshipping Allah and doing good deeds. A Muslim is aware that Allah, s.w.t., knows everything about him/her, because every act is recorded, according to the following hadith: Then he (Jibril, a.s.) further asked, "What is Ihsan (perfection)?" Allah's Messenger (ﷺ) replied, "To worship Allah as if you see Him, and if you cannot achieve this state of devotion then you must consider that He is looking at you." (Sahih al-Bukhari 50)

Taqwa, based on the knowledge of tawhid, is the reason why Muslims all over the world avoid what is haram (forbidden), such as interest, pork, alcohol, immorality etc. despite the fact that these things are allowed in almost all countries in the world now. But taqwa does not only mean avoiding forbidden things, but any act of worship, of doing good things, is the cause of taqwa.

Every action in daily life – buying goods, helping family members, helping employees, pay debts in time – fall under the definition of “acts of worshipping Allah”. This makes worship in Islam different form worship in other religions, faiths

and ideologies. (Abdullah, et al., 2018) All this is summarised in the following ayat of the Qur'an: **“Indeed, Allah orders justice and good conduct and giving to relatives and forbids immorality and bad conduct and oppression. He admonishes you that perhaps you will be reminded.”** (Qur'an, 16:90)

CONSEQUENCES OF BELIEF ON ECONOMIC ACTIONS

A believer, who is aware that God is looking at him, will certainly avoid everything which is forbidden. On the other hand, the lack of ethical rules inevitably leads to an increase of selfish behaviour of economic agents. Self-interest without self-control inevitably will lead to greed, but also to arrogance and envy. It is important to mention that the ignorance of religious values in the capitalistic economic system has not always been a dominant path. Max Weber argued that religious ideas from groups like the Calvinists played a role in shaping the capitalistic spirit. (Weber, 1930) In other words, the Protestant work ethic influenced people to engage in secular work, develop enterprises, and accumulate wealth for investment, contributing to the unplanned emergence of capitalism. So, it is quite necessary to have a strong ethical background for economic development. The constant consciousness about the presence of the Creator, Allah, s.w.t., changes the behaviour of a person. Even if he or she is doing a bad deed, such as taking interest, the person knows that this deed is recorded and the person will be held accountable – no matter a camera has recorded it or whether there have been any human witnesses. Therefore, a person, even if the official legal system allows something prohibited according to religious laws, he/she will avoid it, in order to record a good deed and deserve a place in Paradise. Of course, this does not mean that there is no need for police or any other due diligence in economic transactions, but the level of trust should be much higher in a society where religious values are practised.

Such thinking is completely contrary to a secular system, where people only fear a state authority and if a person thinks that he/she is smarter than this authority, he/she will possibly avoid the laws of a country. Therefore, we can witness more and more unethical behaviour in economic transactions, causing a massive increase in misinformation of stakeholders, insider trading, exploitations, corruption, environmental pollution and fraudulent behaviour. The lack of trust will reduce economic behaviour, especially in the field of finance. When a contracting party fears that the other party will not use the invested money for agreed purposes or will not show the real profits, then the motivation for investments will fall. Continuous monitoring of the other party is not a solution, because someone can always play out the rules.

THE PROHIBITION OF RIBA (INTEREST)

The Rules with Regard to Riba

In Islam, the word “riba” is used for interest. Riba is strongly forbidden in Islamic law. According to Ibn Rushd, the types of riba in Islam can be divided into two groups: (Ibn Rushd, 1996)

1. *Riba buyu* (riba at the exchange of goods):
 - *riba al-fadl* (surplus interest)
 - *riba al-nasi'ah* (delay interest)
2. *Riba duyun* (riba at loans):
 - *riba al-jahiliyya* (lateness interest)
 - *da'wa ta'ajjal* (interest due to pre-payment)

Riba buyu accrues when goods are traded for goods of the same genus in different quantities and/or if there is a delay in a transaction with goods of the same kind. This type of interest is described in the following hadith: “Gold for gold, silver for silver, wheat for wheat, barley for barley, dates for dates, and salt for salt - like for like, equal for equal, and hand-to-hand; if the commodities differ, then you may sell as you wish, provided that the exchange is hand-to-hand.” (Hadith narrated by Muslim and Tirmidhi)

In the hadith, six commodities are mentioned: gold, silver, wheat, barley, dates and salt. Islamic jurists have interpreted this hadith in different ways. One school of thought emphasises the measurability, whereas others the characteristic of these goods as money and foodstuff. Anyway, *riba buyu* can be divided into two groups: *riba al-fadl* and *riba al-nasi'ah*.

Riba al-fadl is defined as follows: “It is an increase in the measure of one of two compensations of the same genus in a sales contract.” (Zuhayli, 2003) Translated into modern financial transactions, this would mean that an exchange of € 1,000 for € 1,050 is strictly forbidden, no matter whether the exchange happens as a spot transaction or with a delay. On the other hand, some items can be exchanged with a surplus, but without delay. If the goods are used as money or as foodstuff (but are of a different genus), then an exchanged with a surplus is allowed, but without a delay. For example, it is allowed to exchange €1,000 for \$1,100, but it must be a spot transaction. This rule avoids hidden transactions with interest. Without this rule, someone could lend €1,000 and ask for \$ 2,000 in one year. In this way, the rules for the prohibition of interest would be bypassed. But, the Prophet, p.b.u.h., has forbidden such transactions, because they contain *riba an-nasi'ah*. But, an exchange of items of a different genus, for example to sell a car on credit for a higher price than the price for cash, is permissible.

Riba duyun can be divided into the following:

- *riba al-jahiliyya* (lateness interest)
- *da'wa ta'ajjal* (interest due to pre-payment)

The main difference between these two types of interest is that in the first type the money lender is the beneficial of a forbidden transaction, whereas at the second type the debtor is the beneficial of a forbidden transaction. *Riba al-jahiliyya* is mentioned in the following *ayat* of the Qur'an: **"O you who have believed, do not consume *riba*, doubled and multiplied, but fear Allah that you may be successful."** (Qur'an, 3:130) *Riba al-jahiliyya* is an excess on the principal which the debtor will have to pay, if he/she is unable to pay back his/her debt on time. All jurists agree that it is strictly forbidden to increase the amount owed in compensation for deferring the payment, regardless of whether the debt resulted from a loan or a sale. (Zuhayli, 2003) On the other hand, interest due to pre-payment accrues when the lender and debtor agree in advance that the lender will decrease the debt, if the debtor will return his/her debt before the stipulated date of repayment. This is forbidden by the jurists of all four juristic schools. (Zuhayli, 2003) This rule is based on the following *ayat* in the Qur'an: **"And if you do not, then be informed of a war [against you] from Allah and His Messenger. But if you repent, you may have your principal - [thus] you do no wrong, nor are you wronged."** (Qur'an, 2:279)

Reasons for the Prohibition of Riba

Analysing the rules regarding *riba*, we can conclude that it is forbidden to exchange items of the same genus with a surplus or exchange similar items with a delay. It is quite clear that if someone is ready to borrow an item and return a higher value of the same item, it can be clearly concluded that this contracting party is exploited by the other party. Ibn al-Qayyim explains the exchange rules for precious metals (money): "(...) as for precious metals and other goods for which interest can accrue, when they are exchanged for the same goods, it is prohibited to go before the physical exchange takes place. This should prevent that this good becomes a source of deferred payment, which is the main cause of interest. In this way, the Prophet, peace be upon him, kept Muslims away from touching with interest, by imposing the condition that the takeover of property must take place at once. Also, in order to prevent to become a means of real interest, he introduced the obligation of equality in the sharing of similar types of goods, even when these goods may have a different quality." (Islahi, 1996) Ibn al-Qayyim connects the mentioning of foodstuffs with their use as money: "When people would be allowed to exchange food on credit, they would do this only when it is profitable and would never sell their goods at once, because they would hope realise a profit by selling them later. In this case, affected people could hardly buy food of their choice, because ordinary people often do not have cash. People, especially in rural areas, carry little cash and usually exchange one type of grain for another. That is why it was wisely and mercifully by the Legislator to prohibit deferred payment in exchange of food items, as He did in the case of precious metals." (Islahi, 1996) Al-Ghazali sees the hoarding of money as a key reason for the existence of interest. He connected hoarding and taking interest by saying: "One who practices interest on Dirhams and Dinars is denying the bounty of Allah and is a transgressor, for these coins are created for other purposes and are not needed for themselves. When someone is trading in Dirhams and Dinars themselves, he is making them as his goal, which is

contrary to their objectives. Money is not created to earn money, and doing, so is a transgression (...) The two kinds of money are means to acquire other things; they are not meant for themselves. In relation to other goods, Dirhams and Dinars are like prepositions in a sentence; as the grammarians define them, 'a preposition is that which is used to give proper meaning to words,' or their position is like a mirror reflecting colours (of other things but no colour of its own). If a person is permitted to sell (or exchange) money with money, then such transactions will become his goal, and as a result will be imprisoned and hoarded like anything. Imprisonment of the ruler or a postman is a transgression, for they are then prevented from performing their functions; same is the case with money. It is a transgression." (Ghazanfar & Islahi, 2009)

Therefore, the development of modern Islamic financial products has to be done in such a way, so money holders do not have an economic advantage compared to all other economic agents. Money is needed by all economic agents (no matter whether they are rich or poor), so this big demand can lead to the abuse of the economic power of money holder, who can in such a situation ask for a surplus. In such a case, money, instead of being only medium of exchange, becomes a good, which is desired due to its special characteristics, but not because it is a medium of exchange. Therefore, earning income through interest essentially takes advantage of the misfortune of another party. Islam prohibits the exchange of similar goods with any surplus, ensuring that the essence and purpose of money remain intact.

ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES OF INTEREST (RIBA)

When we look in conventional textbooks about finance, we will always find the formula for the so-called "net present value". Mathematically, the net present value is calculated according to the following formula:

$$NPV = -A_0 + \sum_{t=1}^t \frac{CF_t}{(1+i)^t}$$

where:

- NPV = net present value
- CF = net cash flow during the period t
- t = number of time periods
- i = interest rate (minimal return)
- A₀ = Acquisition Costs in period 0

This formula can be found in some textbooks about Islamic finance, although the authors do not elaborate the theoretical background of the formula. In this case, cash-flows of any future period are discounted with the interest rate of a risk-free alternative (often government bonds). In other words, an investor compares the internal rate of return of an investment with the interest rate of a risk-free alternative. If the investment has a positive net present value, this means that the investor will receive a

higher return on his investment, than putting his money on the interest-based financial product. On the other hand, a negative net present value means that the investment is not able to earn the specified minimal interest, which the investor can receive from the interest-based product.

A simple mathematical analysis of this formula indicates several problems of an interest-based system:

1. If capital markets provide high returns through fixed income securities, investors will likely avoid real investments. Consequently, this will reduce overall investments, shifting economic activity from the real sector to the financial sector. Real sector investments will only become attractive again when interest rates decrease. However, during this period, real sector firms will reduce their economic activities, leading to higher unemployment rates. Therefore, the discount rate acts as a barrier to investment for companies. The higher the discount rate, the lower the likelihood of investments being made. (Bećirović, Plojović, & Ujkanović, 2012)
2. Net present value method suggests that the earned cash flows during the period will be invested again at the same interest rate. Therefore, it is necessary to use resources at a maximum. The following example shows this. We assume that an individual owns productive land, which he/she can manage with the following alternatives:
 - Using the land intensively for 20 years and receive a cash flow of 13,000 in the first year and in the following years cash flows decrease by 10% annually. However after this period, the land cannot be used for productive purposes anymore.
 - The other alternative is the sustainable use of land with an annual cash flow of 6,000, where the land can be used "indefinitely".

The acquisition cost of the land is 50,000 and the investor calculates with an interest rate of 10%.

According to these assumptions the first alternative has a net present value of 13,825, whereas the second alternative has a net present value of only 10,000. If the investment decision is exclusively made according to the net present value, the first alternative will be chosen. However, using this alternative, the land will be unusable after 20 years, so future generations will not be able to use this land anymore and have income from it due to intensive usage. On the other hand, the second alternative would generate an eternal cash flow and future generations could use the land. However, discounting says that higher cash flows at an earlier stage have to be preferred, so extensive exploitation of resources is fostered, because these cash flows can be invested and receive an interest income. Such thinking leads to damages of the environment, exploitation and to selfish behaviour, without considering the interests of future generations. Thus, thinking according to net present value leads to investor behaviour where the distant future is discounted excessively relative to the near future. This is the real reason for time preference, receiving high cash flows as soon as possible to reinvest or consume the earned money as soon as possible. (Bećirović, An analysis of time preference theory of interest and its impact on the business environment, 2015)

3. The net present value compares internal return of an investment with the return of risk-free investments in the capital markets or the interest rate on saving accounts. This means that there will always be a high supply of money, which has to be employed. By borrowing money, total indebtedness of the economic agents will increase, which will lead to economic problems, especially when the economy is not developing according to expectations. For example, if an investor wants to invest €100,000 and expects a ROI of 10%, he/she will be ready to take a loan at 7%, because profit will be at € 3,000. However, if profit falls below the interest rate of 7%, then the investor will be unable to repay the loan.
4. The part of the formula $[(1+i)]^t$ also implies the problem of compound interest. Investors will lend their money again and again, which will inevitably lead to an exponential increase of deposits, which will again be employed. When we apply these assumptions on a macroeconomic level, we will see that the gross domestic product has to grow faster than the average interest rate. But why? We will show the reason by using a simple model with the following inputs:
 - The initial value of the gross domestic product (GDP) is 200 monetary units (MU)
 - The initial value of the savings is 100 MU
 - Annual constant growth rate of GDP is 3%
 - Constant interest rate is 6%

Table 1
COMPARING THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEPOSITS AND GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT (GDP)

Year	Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	Savings	Interest Expenditures	Interest expenditures in % of GDP
0	200	100	0.00	0.00
10	268.8	179.1	10.1	3.8%
20	361.2	320.7	18.2	5.0%
30	485.5	574.3	32.5	6.7%
40	652.4	1028.6	58.2	8.9%
50	876.8	1842.0	104.3	11.9%
Increase	5.9 fold	33.0 fold		

This example shows clearly that savings are growing enormously. Due to compound interest and an interest rate of 6%, savings double every twelfth year. This growing income will also increase consumption and thus increase GDP. Growing savings have the consequence that the share of interest payments on the gross domestic product is also growing. In order to keep a balance between the growth of domestic products and interest payments, the growth of the gross domestic product must be equal to or even higher than the average interest rate. If this balance is not sustained, then interest payments will increase and income from labour (income from dependent work and entrepreneurship) will decrease, so money holders would receive a growing share of

the country's wealth. This model also shows that people would work exclusively to pay interest on their debts, if the growth of GDP is much smaller than the average interest rate. Therefore, investments must rise not only absolutely, but also relatively compared to the savings in order to avoid a recession and massive unemployment. But this solution cannot be efficient on the long-term, because an ongoing increase of investments leads to a decrease of returns. However, an increase of investments in present also leads to higher capacities in the future. These capacities will be used, if there is sufficient demand. Because every company wants to sell as much products as possible, it will be impossible to sell all products, so a number of companies will go bankrupt, because they are unable to sell their products. Furthermore, an endless growth of GDP is impossible, because natural resources are limited. So interest will over the long haul create severe problems for an economy.

UNDERSTANDING GHARAR (EXCESSIVE RISK)

The Definition of Gharar

Literally, the word “gharar” means risk or danger. The word “tagrir”, which is the verbal noun of gharar, describes a situation where someone unknowingly exposes himself or his property to jeopardy. (Al-Dhareer, 1997) This means that one or both contracting parties do not possess enough information about the object of the contract or contain conditions which expose someone to excessive risk. This excessive risk can cause a wealth decrease to one of the contracting parties. Therefore, well-known Professor Mustafa al-Zarqa defines gharar as follows: “It is the sale of probable items whose existence or characteristics are not certain, due to the risky nature that makes it similar to gambling.” (Zuhayli, 2003)

Regarding to financial contracts, the commandment of gharar has the consequence that a client has the right to receive all necessary information during the contract conclusion. For example, an investor has the right to receive detailed information how his profit share is calculated. Furthermore, a client is not allowed to conclude a contact about an object (e.g. service), which existence is not sure in the future. This rule has severe consequences in the commercial insurance and derivative market. For example, in a modern insurance contract, the insured pays regularly premiums to the insurer. However, the insurer only pays damage to the insured, if there is an insured event. So, if such an event will not happen during the period of contract, the insured will not receive a part of his paid money. According to the rules of gharar, such a contract term is not allowed and therefore modern commercial insurance contracts are not allowed in Islam. Therefore, we will have to have a more detailed look on the rules of gharar, in order to avoid this prohibition in modern contracts.

The Economic Consequence of Gharar

Gharar in financial contracts can be found especially in commercial insurance contracts. According to Zuhayli, the insurance contract falls under the ownership contract, which contains a large percentage of risk and guarantees, because the insured

does not know when concluding the contract how much money he needs to invest and how much money he will receive. On the one hand, there is a possibility that already after the payment of the first instalment, there will be damage that must be compensated, or, on the other hand, it may happen that there will never be any damage. Insurance companies, because of this uncertainty, can have large revenues without expenses. (Zuhayli, 2003)

A simple calculation shows this uncertainty. If we assume that a person wants to insure a car, which is valued at €25,000. For this service, the person will have to pay a sum of €1,000. Furthermore, we assume the probability of a damage is at 2%. In this case, we can calculate the profit and losses of the insured and the insurance company according to the following table:

Table 2
PROFIT AND LOSS OF THE INSURANCE COMPANY AND INSURED

Situation	Insurance company	Insured
1: Damage (2%)	-24,000	+24,000
2: No damage (98%)	+1,000	-1,000
Expected profit/loss	+500	-500

If a damage occurs, the insured "wins", because the premium paid is normally less than the damage paid. On the other hand, if no damage occurs, the insured loses his paid premiums. It can be seen that when one side wins, the other side always has to lose. Who will be the winner in this contract depends on the probability of the insured event occurring. If we assume a probability of 2% for a damage, then the insurer would have a profit of €500 from each insured ($-24000 \cdot 2\% + 1000 \cdot 98\%$). The greater the number of insured persons, the greater the insurance company's earnings. Because insurance companies calculate the premium offered based on the probability of an insured event, insurance companies will have a large cash flow from their contracts. This is the explanation why classical insurance companies manage a lot of liquidity and why insurance companies are important investors in the classical financial system. But, on the other hand the insured will pay a premium continuously and probably never experience a damage. (Al-Suwailem, 2006)

CONCLUSION

The goal of this paper was to show pivotal differences between Islamic and conventional finance. Islam strictly forbids the taking and paying of interest. The reason is to avoid the exploitation of the other contracting party by the economically dominant contracting party. This does not mean that the other contracting party is automatically poor or less informed – big companies or countries can depend on loans from the financiers in order to finance investments and current expenses and therefore have to pay an extra amount (interest) in order to receive the necessary money. Such a system inevitably leads to injustices, with effects on everyone, because money is the

general medium of exchange. The development of just financial contracts is not easy as it seems, at least due to two reasons: the economic power of money holders and the legal framework in many countries, which is developed to suit the conventional interest-based system.

Insurance contracts are also part of the economic system. But often the insured pay much more than they will ever benefit. Here, it is necessary to go back to the roots of insurance: facing risks together, without benefitting from someone's damage. By developing cooperative insurance organisations, companies and individuals will bear the risks of damage together, which will increase solidarity among people.

Finally, all rules mentioned with regard *riba* (interest) or *gharar* (excessive risk), as well as other commandments, will only be observed, if people are convinced that they are truly divine commandments. Muslims believe in the commandments mentioned in the Qur'an and Sunnah, and therefore are ready to observe them. But it is necessary to present solutions considering the intentions of these commandments, which can be practically implemented. Imitating conventional solutions and giving them beautiful Arabic names, is not only contrary to the intentions of Islamic teachings, but will not be accepted by the majority of practising Muslims.

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